

Helping Students to Avoid Critical Mistakes/Misunderstands when Using Active Learning/Project-Based Learning Approaches in Teaching Statistical Analysis

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Abstract

Nowadays, active learning/problem-based learning/project-based learning approaches are widely used in many academic programs of various institutions all over the world. It is believed that these approaches will help to train students in a better way, especially in building the skills through self-studying process and through dealing with practical problems. However, the use of these modern teaching/learning approaches does not mean that lecture-based approach should be completely ignored. Anyway, the time allocation of lecture-based approach should be reduced. During the limited time where lectures are delivered in the traditional way, the key requirement is how to equip the students with enough background knowledge so that they can proceed with self-studying or working with projects without committing critical mistakes related to theoretical background. From the author's experience of more than 20 years teaching statistical analysis related courses, this paper aims at identifying and sharing the common misunderstands observed from the students when studying statistical analysis course. These experiences can help to deliver statistical analysis related courses in an effective and efficient manner when using active learning/problem-based learning /project-based learning approaches.

Keywords: Active Learning; Statistical Analysis; Statistical Inferences.

1 Introduction

Statistical analysis has become a very important subject in all academic courses related to engineering study, management science and social science, just to name a few. Statistical analysis will help to withdraw useful conclusions from available datasets which can help the decision makers to make appropriate decisions for many practical problems. Due to the importance of statistical analysis, the course related to statistical analysis has been introduced even in secondary high school level in many countries. At universities, statistical analysis has become a required course in most curricula regardless of the field of study the students registered for. However, to most of students who took courses on statistical analysis, understanding and applying many statistical analysis techniques delivered in the course is not that easy, and hence, they might commit with various critical errors when applying these techniques. From the author's experience of more than 20 years teaching statistical analysis related courses, this paper aims at identifying and sharing the common misunderstands observed from the students when studying statistical analysis course. This issue is very important especially when active learning/problem-based learning/project-based learning approaches are used in delivering statistical courses. When the above-mentioned approaches are used, the lecture time is reduced, and the students are encouraged to learn through self-studying and problem solving. Hence, how to help the students avoid making mistakes when analysing practical datasets and to make correct decisions should be aimed at during the very limited lecture hours allocated for the course. This paper aims at identifying and sharing the common misunderstands observed from the students when studying statistical analysis course. These experiences can help to deliver statistical analysis related courses in an effective and efficient manner when using active learning/problem-based learning/project-based learning approaches.

2 Literature Review

Recognising the fact that traditional methods of teaching statistics are not effective and fails to help the students to apply statistical knowledge to deal with practical problems in the real world, Mustafa (1996) proposed the relevant objectives that should be aimed at to help develop competencies in the fields that do

not require the students to have a strong mathematical/statistical background. These competences include the ability to link statistics and real-world situations, the knowledge of basic statistical concepts, and the ability to synthesize the components of a statistical study and to communicate the results in a clear manner. To serve this purpose, a revised course design approach has been proposed. In introductory statistics courses, many instructors recommended that the courses should place greater emphasis on data collection, graphical display of data, design of experiments, problem solving, and process improvements (Easton et al., 1988; Snee, 1990; Hogg, 1991; Moore, 1992). Following this recommendation, many courses on statistical analysis started with data analysis directly without introducing the theoretical background of statistical analysis techniques, i.e., probability theory. Even though probability concepts were introduced in some of these courses, the less emphasis on mathematical and probabilistic concepts (such as random variables, probability distributions, conditional probability, etc.) has led to the fact that the students failed to develop a real understanding of many basic statistical concepts, and hence, failed to apply these concepts in dealing with practical problems. However, it should be noted that teaching too much probability in statistical course is not good. It will be good if students have learned about probability theory before taking the course on statistical analysis. Otherwise, only the necessary probabilistic concepts needed to understand the derivations of statistical techniques should be introduced (Moore, 1992). A study by Konold (1995) also indicated that inappropriate instruction on probability concepts might fail to provide students with the skills to master statistical reasoning. Emphasizing on the issue of how to help students understand the concept of variation in statistics, Ballman (1997) recommended to change the traditional way of teaching probability with the use of appropriate topics and activities so that the students can easily capture the characteristics of random variation and relate the application of variation in statistics.

In relation to the use of active learning approach in statistical courses, Anderson-Cook and Dorai-Raj (2001) presented an active learning demonstration on the Internet using Java applets to show a poorly designed experiment and then subsequently a well-designed experiment. The framework demonstrates the concepts of randomization and blocking, as well as the need to carefully consider the objective of a study and how well the data collected answer the question of interest. The activity involves student participation and data collection. Later, Anderson-Cook and Dorai-Raj (2003) also proposed a number of applets to help students understand the role of power in hypothesis testing that allow them to obtain numerical values without having to perform any calculations for a variety of scenarios. These applets are introduced from the observations that the concepts of hypothesis testing, trade-offs between Type I and Type II error, and the use of power in choosing an appropriate sample size based on power are usually included in many introductory statistics courses. However, many students do not really understand these ideas, and hence, are unable to apply them in a correct and effective way in real world problems. Anyway, these applets only help the students to avoid mistakes but cannot help them develop an in-depth understanding about those concepts. Aberson et al. (2002) also derived an interactive Web-based tutorial that supplements instruction on statistical power. This tutorial provides several interactive exercises that guide students as they draw multiple samples from various populations and compare results for populations with differing parameters. The sampling exercises utilize an interactive Java applet that graphically demonstrates relationships between statistical power and effect size, null and alternative populations and sampling distributions, and Type I and II error rates. The applet allows students to manipulate the mean and standard deviation of populations, sample sizes, and Type I error rate. However, the same question on if the students really understand those concepts is still remained.

In other research lines, Alacaci (2004) investigated the knowledge base necessary for choosing appropriate statistical techniques in applied research. In this study, the author compared knowledge used by six experts and six novices in two types of statistical tasks, i.e., comparing research scenarios from the perspective of choosing a statistical technique, and direct comparison of statistical techniques. From the research results, the author recommended that statistical techniques should be taught in relation to relevant research designs, moreover, conceptual connections between statistical techniques should be explicitly taught. Examining the need of collaboration in learning and teaching statistics, Roseth et al. (2008) provided practical examples of how instructors may apply a cooperative framework to classroom teaching and teacher collaboration. This research aimed to persuade statistics instructors who are reluctant to adopt more student-centered teaching approaches, as well as those instructors who have tried these methods but ultimately returned to the traditional

teacher-centered instruction. Recently, Da Silva and Moura (2020) addressed the problems of teaching statistical concepts in biostatistics where students often experience anxiety caused by the complexity of statistics and might express negative attitudes towards the subject.

For more literature and resources on teaching statistics, the readers are encouraged to read the review report of Becker (1996). Journal of Statistics Education is also a good resource for this purpose. To the best of my knowledge, most research works conducted in the past did not communicate clearly the common mistakes related to understanding of students when taking statistical courses. So, in the paper written here, I would like to share some experiences related to this issue with the hope that it will help the instructors who are in charge of delivering these courses at their institutions to recognise the problems the students usually faced with when taking statistical courses so that the courses can be delivered in an effective and efficient ways with more fun from the students' viewpoint.

3 Common Misunderstands in Studying Statistical Analysis

In this session, the discussions will be firstly on basic descriptive statistics including measures of central tendency, measure of variability, the z-score, and coefficient of variation. Then, discussions on hypothesis testing will be presented with the focuses on how to set the null hypothesis, what are the valid conclusions, and Type II error as well as how to control Type II error which is an issue that many students feel very confused when facing.

3.1 Measures of Central Tendency

Measures of central tendency yield information about particular places or locations in a group of numbers. The commonly used measures of central tendency in statistical analysis are mean (or weighted average, expected value), mode and median. When learning these measures, the students usually don't know when to use each of them, especially mode and median. It is noted that the mean value is familiar with all students, and later, nearly all statistical analysis techniques will be derived based on the mean. But why the mean is a good representative for a dataset? Why not use mode and median? In which cases, mode and median are better measures instead of the mean? The reason why the mean of a dataset is a good representative of a dataset is because it is an unbiased estimator of the mean of the population from which the dataset is withdrawn from (i.e., the expectation of the mean of a dataset equals to the mean of the population). This property is a requirement for a good estimator (apart from efficiency and consistency properties of an estimator) which can be used to establish confidence interval and to test hypothesis about the mean of population. However, in some practical situations, the use of mean is not appropriate. For instance, in garment industry there is a need to determine the modal sizes (i.e., S, M, L, XL, XXL) of clothing. If the mean is used, the product will not fit with any customers. In such a situation, the mode should be used instead so that the product produced from modal sizes will fit with many customers in each category. Related to the use of median, this measure is appropriate when there exist extreme values in the dataset. In such a case, the mean will give biased information about the dataset, and hence, it is better to use median because this measure is not affected by extreme values. Anyway, it should be noted that there exist no statistical analysis techniques using mode or median. Therefore, in order to employ the mean for further analysis, the extreme values (or outliers) in the dataset should be excluded. Related to the determination of outliers, many students (and also some statistical software packages) use the range which is defined by three standard deviations from the mean (especially for the case when the population is assumed to follow normal distribution), and any value located outside this range will be considered as outliers. This is a wrong way to determine the outliers that many students committed when studying statistics.

3.2 Measures of Variability

Measures of variability describe the spread or the dispersion of a dataset. The most commonly used measures of variability in statistical analysis are variance and standard deviation. Mathematically, the standard deviation is just the square root of the variance. But why need both? This is a question that most students cannot answer, and hence, they may apply those concepts in a wrong way. It should be noted that the variance of a

dataset (or sample) S^2 can be used to approximate the variance of the population σ^2 , but the standard deviation of a dataset, S , cannot be used to approximate the standard deviation of the population, σ . The reason behind this is that the expected value of S^2 is exactly the same as the variance of the population σ^2 (i.e., $E[S^2] = \sigma^2$), and hence, S^2 is an unbiased estimator of σ^2 . However, the expected value of S is not the same as the variance of the population σ (i.e., $E[S] \neq \sigma$), and hence, S is not an unbiased estimator of σ . Anyway, when the sample size is large enough, we will have $E[S] \approx \sigma$, and therefore, σ can be approximated by S .

3.3 The z-score

The z-score (or the standardized value) of a specific value in a dataset is a measure in term of how many standard deviations the value is different from the mean of a dataset. In fact, it is impossible to say that the absolute difference between a specific value and the mean is small, medium, or large. Therefore, to have a clear picture about this difference, the z-score should be used. For instance, if we look at the difference between the monthly salary of an engineer working in a manufacturing plant and the mean salary of the group of engineers working in the same functional department, we cannot say anything about the position of that engineer in the department and his authority in the group. But the z-score of his monthly salary will reveal such an information. If the z-score is negative, that engineer does not perform well; if the z-score is between 0 and 1, the engineer performs normally but he is just a normal engineer in the group; if the z-score is between 1 and 1.5, he is a good engineer; and if his z-score is greater than 1.5, he performs excellently, and hence, some authority has been vested on him. In quality control, the z-score is also usually used to identify if the shift in mean of the proves is small, medium, or large (e.g., <1 : small; $1-1.5$: medium; >1.5 : large). Then, appropriate control charts will be derived to monitor the process (e.g., the Shewhart control charts can be used to help detect medium to large shifts, CUSUM or EWMA control charts can be used to detect small shifts).

3.4 Coefficient of Variation

Coefficient of variation is a measure of relative dispersion in the dataset. It is determined as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean, expressed as percentage. Similar to the z-score, the coefficient of variation will reveal the true information about variation in the dataset. In many practical problems, using standard deviation alone will not help the analysts to conclude that variation in the dataset if high or low. For instance, when observing records on demand of a product, if the average weekly demand is 100 units/week with the corresponding standard deviation is 20 units/week, then the coefficient of variation is 20% which means that the demand variability is high. However, if the standard deviation of demand is still 20 units/week but the average weekly demand is 1000 units/week, then the coefficient of variation is only 2%. In such a case, the demand rate can be considered as a constant (i.e., not change). Using coefficient of variation will help the students to determine if a deterministic model or a stochastic model should be use when analyzing the dataset.

3.5 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing can be used to determine whether a statement about the value of a population parameter should or should not be rejected. The common procedure recommended in many textbooks for testing hypothesis is as follows:

- Establish hypotheses: state the null and alternative hypotheses.
- Determine the appropriate statistical test and sampling distribution.
- Specify the Type I error rate α
- State the decision rule.
- Gather sample data.
- Calculate the value of the test statistic.
- State the statistical conclusion.

The common mistake that many students made in step 7 is to conclude that “Accept the null hypothesis”. It should be noted that the null hypothesis is just an assumption and the ultimate target when conducting the test is to find evidence to reject the null hypothesis. So, if there exists evidence to reject the null hypothesis then the statement in the alternative hypothesis can be confirmed (with the probability of error α , called Type I error). However, in case the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, it should not be accepted. In this situation,

the assumption stated in the null hypothesis is still valid, but it is true or not we don't really know. The decision to accept the null hypothesis might lead to a very high error (Type II error β).

Another mistake usually observed from students in social sciences and management is that they usually establish the null hypothesis in a wrong way. For instance, H_0 : Price has effect on demand. It should be noted that the assumption in the null hypothesis should point to a unique scenario because we need to have a unique assumed distribution for the population to help conduct the test. The assumption stated in the above null hypothesis does not satisfy this requirement (i.e., has effect! How large??). Instead, the above null hypothesis should be stated as H_0 : Price has no effect on demand. It should be also noted here that if the null hypothesis H_0 : Price has effect on demand is used in the test, there is no way to confirmed that price is actually has effect on demand (this is usually the target of this test) because we are not allow to say that the null hypothesis is accepted.

One interesting point related to hypothesis testing is also about the one-tailed test. In one-tailed test, such as the right-tailed test for the mean of population $H_0: \mu = \mu_0$; $H_a: \mu > \mu_0$, the students usually did not recognize that this test seems to violate the basic requirement in which the statements in the null hypothesis and the alternative hypothesis must be collectively exhaustive. So, the correct establishment should be $H_0: \mu \leq \mu_0$; $H_a: \mu > \mu_0$. However, the null hypothesis $H_0: \mu \leq \mu_0$ does not refer to a unique scenario, and hence, the test cannot be conducted because the hypothesized distribution of the population is not well-defined. Due to this, the null hypothesis should be revised to $H_0: \mu = \mu_0$. Can we do this? The answer is certainly yes because the test is considered to provide useful conclusion only when the alternative hypothesis is confirmed. So, if we cannot confirm this, it means that the original null hypothesis, i.e., $H_0: \mu \leq \mu_0$, is still a valid assumption. This is similar to the problem where we want to prove that a variable (such as μ) is greater than all values in a set, we need to prove that that variable is greater than the maximum value of the set (i.e., μ_0).

Related to using one-tailed test or two-tailed test, it depends on the nature of the problem at hand. For instance, if we want to test if the lifetime of a battery is not different from the nominal lifetime declared by the manufacturer (null hypothesis), the test should be conducted on both tails of the sampling distribution. However, if we want to test if the concentration of a harmful substance in the outflow of a water treatment plant does not violate the regulation on environmental protection (null hypothesis), the test should be conducted on the right tail of the sampling distribution. But in many practical applications, the analyst might convert a two-tailed test into one-tailed test. The reason for this is to enlarge the rejection region so that it is easier to reject the null hypothesis, and hence, the alternative hypothesis can be confirmed.

3.6 Type II Error

Type II error β is the probability to conclude that the null hypothesis is "accepted" when in fact it is false. Type II error is usually very high and it is not under the control of the analyst, especially when the statement in the null hypothesis is not violated too much, and hence, it is difficult for the analyst to find enough evidence to reject it. When analysing Type II error, many students feel very confused because they don't really understand how to determine Type II error and what is the application of this concept. In the course of statistical analysis, the instructors should spend enough time to help the students understand the derivation of the formula used to determine Type II error for the test. For a two-tailed test, the general formula used for determining Type II error is:

$$\beta = \Phi\left(\frac{\mu_0 - \mu_1}{\sigma/\sqrt{n}} + z_{\alpha/2}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{\mu_0 - \mu_1}{\sigma/\sqrt{n}} - z_{\alpha/2}\right)$$

From the above formula, it should be noted that even the analyst cannot control Type II error, but the value of Type II error can be manipulated by increasing sample size. Also, a critical shift (i.e., the shift at which we want to reject the null hypothesis with a high probability) $\delta = \mu_0 - \mu_1$ should be defined. Understanding Type II error and how to manipulate it is very important in many practical situations. For instance, in establishing quality control charts, Type II error must be analysed in order to select an appropriate sample size and sampling frequency so that the control charts can help detect the critical shift in an expected time period.

4 How to Help Students to Avoid Mistakes

In the former sessions, the common misunderstands the students usually committed in studying statistical analysis have been shared. How to help students to avoid making mistakes is a very challenging issue. Using traditional teaching/learning approaches with home assignments/exams will not help. In fact, active learning/problem-based learning/project-based learning approaches can be employed for this purpose. Following the above-mentioned learning approaches, it is recommended that the lecturers should request the students to work in groups to deal with practical problems/projects. Through these group projects, the students are encouraged to apply statistical knowledge to analyse the existing problems, find the root causes of the problems based on historical data, test the efficiency/effectiveness of various possible solutions, and finally, select the best solution for the problem at hand with sound statistical evidences. Inappropriate decisions making during the analysis process will become learning lessons for the students and help them to digest the knowledge with the hope that they will not make similar mistakes in their future career.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, some mistakes and misunderstands the students may commit when studying statistical analysis courses are communicated and shared. Helping the students to avoid these mistakes/misunderstands will help to build confidence in them when applying statistics in dealing with practical problems, and also help them to study more complicated statistical analysis techniques without facing any big problems. These experiences are shared with the hope that active learning/problem-based learning/project-based learning approaches can be launched in an efficient and effective manner for courses on statistical analysis.

6 References

- Aberson, C.L., Berger, D.E., Healy, M.L., and Romero, V.L. (2002) An Interactive Tutorial for Teaching Statistical Power. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 10(3), DOI: 10.1080/10691898.2002.11910682
- Alacaci, C. (2004). Inferential Statistics: Understanding Expert Knowledge and its Implications for Statistics Education. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 12(2), DOI:10.1080/10691898.2004.11910737
- Anderson-Cook, C.M., and Dorai-Raj, S. (2001). An Active Learning In-Class Demonstration of Good Experimental Design. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 9(1), DOI:10.1080/10691898.2001.11910645
- Anderson-Cook, C.M., and Dorai-Raj, S. (2003) Making the Concepts of Power and Sample Size Relevant and Accessible to Students in Introductory Statistics Courses using Applets. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 11(3), DOI: 10.1080/10691898.2003.11910721
- Ballman, K. (1997). Greater Emphasis on Variation in an Introductory Statistics Course. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 5(2), DOI: 10.1080/10691898.1997.11910529
- Becker, B.J. (1996). A Look at the Literature (and Other Resources) on Teaching Statistics. *Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics*, 21(1), 71-90.
- Da Silva, H.A., and Moura, A.S. (2020). Teaching Introductory Statistical Classes in Medical Schools using RStudio and R Statistical Language: Evaluating Technology Acceptance and Change in Attitude towards Statistics. *Journal of Statistics Education*, DOI: 10.1080/10691898.2020.1773354
- Easton, G., Roberts, H. V., and Tiao, G. C. (1988). Making Statistics More Effective in Schools of Business. *Journal of Business and Economic Statistics*, 6, 247-260
- Hogg, R. V. (1991). Statistical Education: Improvements Are Badly Needed. *The American Statistician*, 45, 342-343.
- Konold, C. (1995). Issues in Assessing Conceptual Understanding in Probability and Statistics. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 3(1), DOI:10.1080/10691898.1995.11910479
- Moore, D. S. (1992). "Teaching Statistics as a Respectable Subject," in *Statistics for the Twenty-First Century*, eds. Florence Gordon and Sheldon Gordon, MAA Notes No. 26, Washington: Mathematical Association of America, pp. 14-25.
- Mustafa, R.Y. (1996). The Challenges of Teaching Statistics to Non-specialists. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 4(1). DOI: 10.1080/10691898.1996.11910504
- Roseth, C.J., Garfield, J.B., and Ben-Zvi, D. (2008) Collaboration in Learning and Teaching Statistics. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 16(1), DOI:10.1080/10691898.2008.11889557
- Snee, R. D. (1990). Statistical Thinking and Its Contribution to Total Quality. *The American Statistician*, 44, 116-121.